

DAMAGE GROWTH IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES
WITH INTERLEAVES

Autar K. Kaw
Ph.D. Student
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Clemson University
Clemson, SC 29634-0921
USA

and

James G. Goree
Professor
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Clemson University
Clemson, SC 29634-0921
USA

ABSTRACT

The influence of interleaves on the fracture behavior of laminated composites is investigated. The geometry of the composite consists of a cracked layer, bonded between two half-planes, which is separated by thin, low modulus, interleaves. The interleaves are modeled as uncoupled tension and shear springs. A stress analysis is carried out for a crack which may grow up to and spread along the interface. Integral transform techniques are used to develop the solution in terms of singular integral equations. An asymptotic analysis reveals logarithmic singularities in the critical stresses for the case of a broken layer. The equations are solved numerically and the effect of damage on critical stresses is studied. Initial results indicate that the interleaf gives a significant reduction in stresses in the adjacent regions and, if properly selected, should result in a more damage tolerant laminate.

INTRODUCTION

Laminated composite materials such as graphite/epoxy are being used in structural aircraft components at an increasing rate. The advantages of these materials, however, are significantly reduced because of the relatively low interfacial damage tolerance (fiber fracture

and delamination) due to low velocity impacts, to which aircrafts are susceptible both during manufacturing and service. One suggested method to improve this damage tolerance is to toughen the interfaces by adding thin interleaves between plies. Experimental results presented by Sun [1] do, in fact, indicate that such adhesive layers are effective in suppressing interply damage. Similar results are reported by Masters [2]. The detailed analysis of such laminated composites with interleaves has, however, not been given adequate analytical treatment.

The intent of this study is then to develop a fracture and crack growth model, and to investigate the predicted influence of the interleaf on damage growth in laminated composites. For example, an initial damage in the form of a crack embedded in a ply may propagate through the ply and then either cross over, or grow along, the interface. The influence of the adhesive layer at the interface on such behavior is studied as a function of thickness and relative material properties of the interleaf and the various plies. The geometry considered is shown in Figure 1.

A number of related fracture problems have been solved based on two-dimensional or axisymmetric approximations. The case of a crack perpendicular to a material interface is considered in [3-7], and that of a T-shaped crack located at the interface of two bonded half-planes is presented in [8]. Gecit and Erdogan [9] developed an analytical model for including the effects of the properties and thickness of adhesive layers in periodic strips with cracks perpendicular to the interface. All these solutions were developed in terms of Cauchy-type generalized singular integral equations, and were typically solved using Gauss-Jacobi numerical techniques [4]. A similar approach is used in the present study.

FORMULATION

Consider a laminated composite (Figure 1) in plane strain, or generalized plane stress, consisting of a single layer (Material 1) of width $2h$, shear modulus μ_1 , and Poisson's ratio ν_1 ; and half-planes (Material 2) having shear modulus μ_2 , and Poisson's ratio ν_2 . This is an idealization of a many layered composite where one concentrates on a single layer and approximates the outer layers by half-planes having some average elastic properties. The strip and the half-planes are separated by thin interleaves of thickness t , shear modulus μ_3 and Young's modulus E_3 . A crack of length $2a$ ($a < h$) is located centrally along the x -axis and a split length of length $2c$ may also grow symmetrically along the interface.

The interleaves are modeled as uncoupled tension and shear springs. A significant simplification results from this assumption as discussed by Gecit and Erdogan [9]. The normal and shear spring stiffnesses are given by

$$k_n = \frac{E_0}{t}, \text{ and}$$

$$k_s = \frac{\mu_3}{t}, \text{ with}$$

$E_0 = E_3/(1-\nu_3^2)$ for generalized plane stress, and

$= E_3(1-\nu_3)/(1+\nu_3)(1-2\nu_3)$ for plane strain.

The displacement field for the cracked layer (Material 1) is given by the superposition of the transformed solutions [10] for an uncracked strip, and an infinitely large region having a crack along the x-axis, with $x = 0$, $y = 0$ as planes of symmetry. It may be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_1(x,y) &= -\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \left\{ \frac{1}{\eta} [f_1(\eta) - \frac{\kappa_1 - 1}{2} g_1(\eta)] \sinh(\eta x) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + x g_1(\eta) \cosh(\eta x) \right\} \cos(\eta y) d\eta \\
 &\quad - \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\phi_1(\xi)}{\xi} \left(\frac{\kappa_1 - 1}{2} - \xi y \right) e^{-\xi y} \sin(\xi x) d\xi \\
 v_1(x,y) &= \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \left\{ \frac{1}{\eta} [f_1(\eta) + \frac{\kappa_1 + 1}{2} g_1(\eta)] \cosh(\eta x) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + x g_1(\eta) \sinh(\eta x) \right\} \sin(\eta y) d\eta \\
 &\quad + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\phi_1(\xi)}{\xi} \left(\frac{\kappa_1 + 1}{2} + \xi y \right) e^{-\xi y} \cos(\xi x) d\xi \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding stress field is given by the equations

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\sigma_{xx}^1(x,y)}{2\mu_1} &= -\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty [f_1(\eta) \cosh(\eta x) + \eta x g_1(\eta) \sinh(\eta x)] \cos(\eta y) d\eta \\
 &\quad - \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \phi_1(\xi) (1 - \xi y) e^{-\xi y} \cos(\xi x) d\xi \\
 \frac{\sigma_{yy}^1(x,y)}{2\mu_1} &= \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \{ [f_1(\eta) + 2g_1(\eta)] \cosh(\eta x) + \eta x g_1(\eta) \sinh(\eta x) \} \\
 &\quad \cos(\eta y) d\eta \\
 &\quad - \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \phi_1(\xi) (1 + \xi y) e^{-\xi y} \cos(\xi x) d\xi \\
 \frac{\sigma_{xy}^1(x,y)}{2\mu_1} &= \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \{ [f_1(\eta) + g_1(\eta)] \sinh(\eta x) + \eta x g_1(\eta) \cosh(\eta x) \} \\
 &\quad \sin(\eta y) d\eta \\
 &\quad - \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \xi y \phi_1(\xi) e^{-\xi y} \sin(\xi x) d\xi \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the displacement and stress fields for the half plane may be expressed as

$$u_2(x, y) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{1}{n} [f_2(n) + \frac{\kappa_2 - 1}{2} g_2(n)] + xg_2(n) \right\} e^{-nx} \cos(ny) dn$$

$$v_2(x, y) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{1}{n} [f_2(n) - \frac{\kappa_2 + 1}{2} g_2(n)] + xg_2(n) \right\} e^{-nx} \sin(ny) dn \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{xx}^2(x, y)}{2\mu_2} = - \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} [f_2(n) + nxg_2(n)] e^{-nx} \cos(ny) dn$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{yy}^2(x, y)}{2\mu_2} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} [f_2(n) + (nx - 2)g_2(n)] e^{-nx} \cos(ny) dn$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{xy}^2(x, y)}{2\mu_2} = - \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} [f_2(n) + (nx - 1)g_2(n)] e^{-nx} \sin(ny) dn. \quad (4)$$

where

$$\kappa_j = 3 - 4\nu_j \text{ for plane strain}$$

$$= \frac{3-4\nu_j}{1+\nu_j} \text{ for plane stress.}$$

Loads are applied parallel to the y -axis and away from the crack region. For the case of a stress-free crack solutions for two problems are superposed. First, the problem of vanishing stresses and displacement at infinity and uniform compression on the notch surface is developed. In order to obtain the complete solution, these results are added to those for an undamaged region with uniform applied strain in the y -direction. The solution to the latter problem is simply uniform axial strain at all points. The solution to the former problem is the intent of this study.

ANALYSIS

Three cases related to the extent of damage are investigated. The first case deals with a symmetric crack within Material 1. In the second case, the crack is allowed to grow up to the interface. The last case accounts for splitting along the interface.

Crack within the layer ($a < h$)

Using the stress and displacement field equations (1-4), and the following boundary and continuity conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma^1_{yy}(x, 0) &= -p_0 & |x| < a \\
v_1(x, 0) &= 0 & a < |x| < h \\
\sigma^1_{xx}(h, y) &= k_n [u_2(h, y) - u_1(h, y)] \\
\sigma^1_{xy}(h, y) &= k_s [v_2(h, y) - v_1(h, y)] \\
\sigma^1_{xx}(h, y) &= \sigma^2_{xx}(h, y); & \sigma^1_{xy}(h, y) &= \sigma^2_{xy}(h, y), \quad (5)
\end{aligned}$$

Cauchy-type singular integral equations are developed using the techniques of Erdogan, et. al. [3-7]. The resulting equation is then solved by using Gauss-Jacobi techniques [4].

Following the techniques given in [5,6] it can be shown that the slope of the crack opening displacement, $\frac{\partial v_1(x, 0)}{\partial x}$, is given by

$$G(x) = \frac{\partial v_1(x, 0)}{\partial x} = \frac{H(x)}{\sqrt{x^2 - a^2}}, \quad |x| < a, \quad (6)$$

where $H(x)$ satisfies the Holder condition, enumerated in [11], in the closed interval $(-a, a)$.

The normal stress in Material 1 at the crack-tip is given by

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a^+} \sigma^1_{yy}(x, 0) = -\frac{4\mu_1}{(1+\kappa_1)} \lim_{x \rightarrow a^-} \frac{\partial v_1(x, 0)}{\partial x} \quad (7)$$

The stress intensity factor K is defined as being the strength of the stress singularity ahead of the crack as given by

$$K = \lim_{x \rightarrow a^+} \sqrt{2(x-a)} \sigma^1_{yy}(x, 0). \quad (8)$$

Crack at the interface (fully broken layer $a = h$)

For the related case in [9] it was shown that the displacement derivative function $G(x)$ had power singularities at the end points. The power of the singularity was found to depend on the relative material properties of the layer and the adhesive. However, the adhesive layers were modeled as a continuum and not as springs. Modeling the interleaf as a spring leads to a logarithmically singular slope function $G(x)$ given by

$$G(x) = \frac{\partial v_1(x, 0)}{\partial x} = H(x) \log(h^2 - x^2), \quad |x| < h, \quad (9)$$

where $H(x)$ satisfies the Holder function.

The normal cleavage stress in Material 2 is given by

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow h^+} \sigma_{yy}^2(x, 0) = \frac{4\mu_3}{\pi h_3} v_1(h, 0) \log(x - h) + 0 \quad (10)$$

Broken layer (a=h) and splitting along the interface

The previous case for the through-crack could have been solved by using a continuum model for the adhesive layer as given in [9]. However, one problem with such a model is that it is very difficult to include delamination along the interface. The spring model, on the other hand, is a close approximation for thin adhesive layers. This model does force the normal and shear stresses to be constant through the thickness of the interleaf, but since the interleaf thickness is small, it is felt to be a good approximation.

The slope of the crack-opening displacement is now bounded at $x = h$ and has no singularities at the end points ($x = \pm h$). However, the stresses in Materials 1 and 2 do have logarithmic singularities at the ends of the split ($y = c$) with the normal stresses given by

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow c^+} \sigma_{yy}^1(h, y) = -\frac{2\mu_3}{\pi h_3} [v_2(h, c) - v_1(h, c)] \log(y - c) + 0(1)$$

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow c^+} \sigma_{yy}^2(h, y) = \frac{2\mu_3}{\pi h_3} [v_2(h, c) - v_1(h, c)] \log(y - c) + 0(1) \quad (11)$$

RESULTS

Some limited initial results are presented below both to demonstrate the validity of the solution, and to consider the influence of the interleaf on the axial stresses in the undamaged region. Extensive results as well as a complete discussion of the analysis and solution can be found in the NASA final report for this grant, to be completed in October, 1987.

The material properties chosen for the following examples are

$$E_1 = 10.35 \text{ MPa}, \quad \nu_1 = 0.28,$$

$$E_2 = 182.90 \text{ MPa}, \quad \nu_2 = 0.28, \text{ and}$$

$$E_3 = 3.45 \text{ MPA}, \quad \nu_3 = 0.35.$$

Figure 2 describes the variation of the normalized stress intensity factor, defined by equation (8), as a function of interleaf thickness for two values of crack length. As the interleaf thickness increases the stress intensity factor increases, and correctly approaches that of a finite width strip with stress-free boundaries.

Figures 3 and 4 depict the axial stress in the undamaged region for a fully broken layer, $a = h$, with no longitudinal splitting ($c = 0$), and with disbonding of $c = 0.05h$. Both figures also include

results for $a = 0.9h$ for comparison. Figure 3 is for the case of an interleaf thickness of $t = 0.2h$ and Figure 4 for $t = 0.3h$. It is clear that the broken layer gives a significant increase in the axial stress in region 2 as compared to the embedded crack ($a = 0.9h$). It is equally clear that for the broken layer, $a = h$, the effect of longitudinal splitting is to reduce the axial stress near $x = h$. Also, by comparing Figures 3 and 4, an increase in the interleaf thickness from $0.2h$ to $0.3h$ substantially reduces the axial stress. The stresses are, of course, logarithmically singular at the crack-tip (h, c). But, in the manner of a point stress failure criterion, at $x = 1.02h, y = c$, the results from Figure 3 give $\sigma_{yy}^2(1.02h, c)/p_0 = 2.2$, and Figure 4 gives $\sigma_{yy}^2(1.02h, c)/p_0 = 1.9$. Similar findings apply for delamination growth. These are discussed in detail in the presentation as well as in the NASA report.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank the Fatigue and Fracture Branch, Materials Division of the NASA Langley Research Center, Hampton, Virginia (USA) for their support of this work under NASA Grant NAG-1-629. The monitor of this project is Dr. Kevin O'Brien.

Figure 1. Laminate containing a broken ply with interleaves between plies.

Figure 2. Stress intensity factor K as a function of interleaf thickness for fixed crack length.

Figure 3. Normalized axial stress in Material 2 as a function of distance from the interface for fixed interleaf thickness ($t = 0.2h$).

Figure 4. Normalized axial stress in Material 2 as a function of distance from the interface for fixed interleaf thickness ($t = 0.3h$).

REFERENCES

1. Sun C. T., Suppression of Delamination in Composite Laminates Subjected to Impact Loading. 11th Annual Mechanics of Composites Review, Dayton, Ohio, pp. 106-113, October 1985.
2. Masters, J. E., Characterization of Impact Damage Development in Graphite/Epoxy Laminates. ASTM Symposium on Fractography of Modern Engineering Materials, Nashville, Tennessee, November 1985.
3. Erdogan, F., Simultaneous Dual Integral Equations with Trigonometric and Bessel Kernels. *Z. Angew. Mathematik Mechanik*, Band 48, Heft 4, pp. 217-225, (1968).
4. Erdogan, F., Gupta, G. D., and Cook, T. S., Methods of Analysis and Solutions of Crack Problems (Chapter 7). Editor Sih, G. C., Noordhoff International Publication, (1973).
5. Erdogan, F., and Gupta, G. D., Layered Composites with an Interface Flaw. *Int. J. Solids Structures*. Vol. 7, pp. 1089-1107, (1971).
6. Erdogan, F., and Gupta, G. D., The Stress Analysis of Multi-Layered Composites with a Flaw. *Int. J. Solids Structures*. Vol. 7, pp. 39-61, (1971).

7. Civelik, M. B., Erdogan, F., and Cakiroglu, A. O., Interface Separation for an Elastic Layer Loaded by a Rigid Stamp. Int. J. Solids Structures, Vol. 16, pp. 669-679, (1978).
8. Goree, J. G., and Venezia, W. A., Bonded Elastic Half-Planes with an Interface Crack and a Perpendicular Intersecting Crack. I. J. Engr. Science, Vol. 15, No. 1, Part 1, pp. 1-17; Part 2, pp. 19-27, (1977).
9. Gecit, M. R. and Erdogan, F., The Effect of Adhesive Layers on the Fracture of Laminated Structures. J. Engg. Mats. and Tech., Transactions of ASME, Paper No. 77-WA/Mat-4, (1977).
10. Hilton, P. D., and Sih, G. C., A Laminate Composite with a Crack Normal to the Interfaces. Int. J. Solids Structures, Vol. 7, pp. 913-930, (1971).
11. Muskhelishvili, N. I., Singular Integral Equations. Noordhoff International Publication, (1953).
12. Sneddon, I. N., and Lowengrub, M., Crack Problems in the Classical Theory of Elasticity. pp. 62-72, John Wiley, (1969).